

Authoritative and Authoritarian Parenting Styles as Factors in the Grit Scores of Selected College Students

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ABSTRACT

This study attempted to confirm locally what other studies have found concerning how a particular parenting style is positively related to grit. A 30-item parenting style questionnaire, which identifies authoritarian, authoritative or permissive parenting styles and initially created for parent-respondents was modified for the point of view of the child. 60 college students studying in a government school in Rizal, Philippines whose parents are alive and staying together, volunteered to take part in this study. 35 respondents were identified as having undergone authoritative parenting style, while 25 respondents were identified as having undergone authoritarian parenting style. Their grit scores were then obtained using the Short Grit Scale. The Welch's T-test yielded a very statistically significant difference between the grit scores of both groups of respondents. Furthermore, since the mean of the grit scores of respondents identified as having undergone authoritative parenting style is higher, it can be inferred that an authoritative parenting style promotes higher grit among this particular set of respondents.

Keywords: Parenting Style, Grit, Authoritative, Authoritarian

INTRODUCTION

The Theory on Parenting Styles is based on the work of Diana Baumrind and researchers from Stanford, Eleanor Maccoby and John Martin. According to this theory, there are four major parenting styles namely, authoritative, authoritarian, permissive and neglectful.¹ These four

parenting styles have close relationships with children's behavior. Each parenting style can produce varying child development and behavior outcomes.²

Parental monitoring and involvement have been found to be strong predictors of adolescent achievement. Authoritative parenting styles are usually connected with higher academic achievement but such findings are not consistent across culture, ethnicity and socioeconomic status.³

In one study, it was found that the style of the parent-child relationship is an effective factor in promoting resilience in children.⁴ Higher levels of physical activity in children was found to be associated with maternal permissive parenting but depended on child gender and the kind of physical activity.⁵

In another study, children of authoritarian parenting style showed higher scores of depersonalization and anxiety. In addition, children of authoritative and permissive styles of parenting exhibited highest scores on active problem coping.⁶ Parenting styles that manifested "acceptance-involvement" and "psychological autonomy-granting" were significant positive predictors of children's self-esteem.⁷

According to one study, parenting practices were significantly linked to the prosocial behaviors of adolescents, but this occurred indirectly through sympathy.⁸ A study has also revealed that authoritarian parenting styles promotes rebelliousness in children, which leads to their problematic behavior. However, the authoritative parenting style

was found to be more effective in exerting influence over a child's behavior.⁹

A significant negative relationship was established between a mother's authoritarian parenting style and grit of children of both sexes.¹⁰ Grit is a construct that encompasses passion and perseverance for long-term goals. A study has found that significant relationships exist between specific parenting styles and grit.¹¹ Overparenting, parental acceptance and involvement were also established as having significant relationships to grit. Grit was also demonstrated as possessing a significant predictive relationship with academic achievement.¹²

For this study, the focus is on authoritative and authoritarian parenting styles, which this research found to be the more common types practiced among Filipino families.

Parents that utilize the authoritative parenting style are responsive to the needs of the child, are flexible, they listen and give advice, they encourage children to be independent, assertive but respectful, they rely on reason and sets reasonable expectations and rules and explains them.¹³

In the authoritarian parenting style, children are expected to obey stringent rules. Disobedience normally entails punishment for the child. Parents do not explain the reason for the rules. They simply insist on them because they are the parents. Such parents have high demands but gives little guidance and are not responsive to their children.¹⁴

A parenting style questionnaire¹⁵ initially developed for parent-respondents, was modified to be answered by child-respondents, which produced results that identified the perceived parenting style experienced by the respondents. The Short Grit Scale¹⁶ was used to measure the respondents' grit.

The objective of this research was to confirm the findings of one study that connects parenting style to grit.¹¹

Specifically, this study addressed the following research questions:

1. What are the levels of grit of respondents who perceive themselves as having undergone authoritative parenting style?
2. What are the levels of grit of respondents who perceive themselves as having undergone authoritarian parenting style?
3. Is there a significant relationship difference between the grit scores of respondents who perceive themselves as having underwent authoritative and authoritarian parenting styles?

METHODOLOGY

A 30-item parenting style questionnaire,¹⁵ which identifies authoritarian, authoritative or permissive parenting styles and originally designed for parent-respondents was modified for the point of view of the child. The questionnaire uses a 6-point scale from *never to always*. 60 college students from a government school in Rizal, Philippines volunteered to take part in this study. All of them were pre-selected to satisfy the criteria that both their parents are living and presently staying together (not separated). After administering the modified parenting style questionnaire, the parenting style of a respondent is identified by looking at the highest score obtained among authoritative, authoritarian and permissive styles. 35 respondents were identified as having undergone authoritative parenting style, while 25 respondents were identified as having undergone authoritarian parenting style. Their grit scores were then obtained using the Short Grit Scale, which is composed of 8 items and uses a 5-point scale. The results were compared using statistical analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1: Modified Parenting Questionnaire Used

Authoritative Style Items		Never 1 2 3 4 5 6 Always
1. My parent is responsive to my feelings and needs		
2. My parent considers my wishes before my parent asks me to do something		
3. My parent explains to me how he/she feels about my good behavior and bad behavior:		
4. My parent encourages me to talk about my feelings and problems		
5. My parent encourages me to freely speak my mind, even if I disagree with my parent		
6. My parent explains the reasons behind his/her expectations		
7. My parent provides comfort and understanding when I am upset		
8. My parent compliments me.		
9. My parent considers my preferences when he/she makes plans for the family like weekend activities, trips or holidays		
10. My parent respects my opinions and encourages me to express them		
11. My parent treats me as an equal member of the family		
12. My parent provides me reasons for the expectations he/she has for me		
13. My parent has warm and intimate times together with me		
Scoring: Total score ____ / 13 =		
Authoritarian Style Items		Never 1 2 3 4 5 6 Always
14. When I ask my parent why he/she wants me to do something, my parent answers "because I said so, I am your parent and that is what I want"		
15. My parent punishes me by taking privileges away (I am prohibited from going out or using my phone or watching movies)		
16. My parent yells when he/she disapproves of my behavior		
17. My parent explodes in anger towards me		
18. My parent spanks me when he/she doesn't like what I do or say		
19. My parent criticizes me to make me improve my behavior		
20. My parent uses threats as a form of punishment with little or no justification		
21. My parent punishes me by not showing emotional affection		
22. My parent openly criticizes me when my behavior does not meet his/her expectations		
23. My parent appears to struggle in trying to change how I think or feel about things		
24. My parent feels the need to point out my past behavior problems to make sure I will not do them again		
25. My parent reminds me that he/she is my parent		
26. My parent reminds me of all the things he/she is doing for me and have done for me		
Scoring: Total score ____ / 13 =		
Permissive Style Items		Never 1 2 3 4 5 6 Always
27. My parent finds it difficult to discipline me		
28. My parent gives in to me when I become emotional		
29. My parent spoils me		
30. My parent ignores my bad behavior		
Scoring: Total score ____ / 4 =		

Table 2: Profile of the Respondents

	Male	Female	N	Mean age
Authoritative	8	27	35	22.34
Authoritarian	3	22	25	21.64

Table 3: Grit of Respondents who underwent Authoritative Parenting Style

Item	Weighted Mean N=35
1. New ideas and projects sometimes distract me from previous ones. *	2.8
2. Setbacks don't discourage me.	3.29
3. I have been obsessed with a certain idea or project for a short time but later lost interest. *	3.11
4. I am a hard worker.	3.83
5. I often set a goal but later choose to pursue a different one. *	3.17
6. I have difficulty maintaining my focus on projects that take more than a few months to complete. *	3.31
7. I finish whatever I begin.	4
8. I am diligent.	3.94
*Reverse-scored items	
Grand weighted mean	3.43125

Table 4: Grit of Respondents who underwent Authoritarian Parenting Style

Item	Weighted Mean N=25
1. New ideas and projects sometimes distract me from previous ones. *	2.32
2. Setbacks don't discourage me.	3.04
3. I have been obsessed with a certain idea or project for a short time but later lost interest. *	2.4
4. I am a hard worker.	3.96
5. I often set a goal but later choose to pursue a different one. *	2.6
6. I have difficulty maintaining my focus on projects that take more than a few months to complete. *	2.28
7. I finish whatever I begin.	4.04
8. I am diligent.	3.76
*Reverse-scored items	
Grand weighted mean	3.05

Table 5: Comparison of Grit of Respondents of Authoritative and Authoritarian Parenting Styles

Group	Authoritative	Authoritarian
Mean	3.43214	3.05000
SD	0.50398	0.50518
SEM	0.08519	0.10104
N	35	25

Table 6: Difference of Grit of Respondents of Authoritative and Authoritarian Parenting Styles

Welch's T-test	
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.0056 By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be very statistically significant.	Confidence interval: The mean of Authoritative minus Authoritarian equals 0.38214 95% confidence interval of this difference: From 0.11683 to 0.64746
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 2.8916 df = 51 standard error of difference = 0.132	

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the modified version of the parenting style questionnaire used in this study to identify the respondent's perceived parenting style experienced.

It can be observed in Table 2 that out of the 60 respondents, the respondents who perceive themselves as having undergone authoritative parenting style had 8 males and 27 females and had a mean age of 22.34. The respondents who perceive themselves as having undergone authoritarian parenting style had 3 males and 22 females and had a mean age of 21.64.

Table 3 shows the weighted mean for each of the 8 items of the Short Grit Scale as answered by the respondents who perceive themselves as having undergone authoritative parenting style. On the other hand, Table 4 shows the weighted mean for each of the 8 items of the Short Grit Scale as answered by the respondents who perceive themselves as having undergone authoritarian parenting style.

The comparison of respondents who perceive themselves as having undergone authoritative parenting style and respondents who perceive themselves as having undergone authoritarian parenting style can be seen in Table 5. It can be noted that the mean of the former is higher than the mean of the latter.

Table 6 shows the Welch's T-test calculation of the grit scores between respondents who perceive themselves as

having undergone authoritative parenting style and respondents who perceive themselves as having undergone authoritarian parenting style. The results revealed that there exists a very statistically significant difference between the two groups of respondents. And because the mean of the grit scores of the group of the authoritative parenting style is higher than the group of the authoritarian parenting style, it can be inferred that an authoritative parenting style promotes a higher grit in the respondents.

CONCLUSIONS

Although this study is limited by the sample and the sampling technique used, the findings do confirm what the previous studies have established concerning the advantages of an authoritative parenting style. Further studies are recommended in order to ascertain what other advantages an authoritative parenting style may yield.

Declaration by Authors

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